

Learning-Based Reconstruction of Under-Sampled MRI Data Using End-to-End Deep Learning in Comparison to CS

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Abstract: Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) reconstruction, particularly restoration and denoising, remains challenging due to its ill-posed nature and high computational demands. In response to this, Compressed Sensing (CS) has recently gained prominence for enabling image reconstruction from limited measurements and consequently reducing computational costs. However, CS often struggles to maintain diagnostic image quality and strictly relies on sparsity and incoherence conditions that are somewhat challenging to meet with experimental data or particularly real-world medical data. To address these limitations, this paper proposes a novel framework that integrates CS with a convolutional neural network (CNN), effectively relaxing the CS constraints and enhancing the diagnostic quality of MRI reconstructions. In essence, this method applies CS to generate a measurement vector during initial step and then refined the output by CNN to improve image quality. Extensive evaluations on the MRI knee dataset demonstrate the efficacy of this dual step approach, achieving significant quality improvements with measurements (SSIM = 0.876, PSNR = 27.56 dB). A deep comparative analysis also perform to identify the superior performance over multiple existing CNN architectures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has gained significant attention in medical imaging due to its exceptional ability to produce high-resolution images surpassing other modalities like CT scans and X-rays. Nevertheless, despite being a highly effective diagnostic tool, MRI frequently has a significant limitation: its lengthy acquisition time. This means that patients often have to lie still for long periods during the scan, which can be uncomfortable and inconvenient. As a result, one of the primary goals in MRI research has been finding ways to shorten these scan times.

To this end, an important technique known as Parallel Imaging (PI) has been introduced (Griswold et al., 2005). This method leverages multiple coils to capture different views of the body simultaneously, which are then combined through software to create the final image. PI techniques are generally divided into two main categories: those that operate in the imaging domain and those that work with k-space data (Ying et al., 2006). Using k-space data more efficiently and applying the Fourier Transform (FT) to make it sparse helps accelerate the imaging process, but it also introduces under-sampling artifacts that can

degrade image quality (Brau et al., 2008).

To accelerate MRI further, researchers have turned to CS (Sartoretti et al., 2019). By acquiring only a subset of the data needed for a full scan, CS-based techniques can reconstruct images faster and at a lower computational cost. Combined with PI, this approach offers a promising way to produce high-resolution MRI images more quickly. However, reconstructing high-quality images from this limited data remains a challenging and hence an active area of research.

Although CS-based approaches have indeed made progress in speeding up MRI reconstruction (Lustig et al., 2008) (Feng et al., 2017), they often come with their own set of problems. On one hand, these methods can reduce the time it takes to reconstruct an image, but with the cost of compromising the diagnostic quality and relying on complex, iterative algorithms that are computationally demanding. In some cases, it may take more time to reconstruct just one image, which makes real-time MRI reconstruction impractical. Moreover, CS-based techniques depend heavily on certain mathematical conditions, like sparsity and incoherence (Provost and Lesage, 2008), which are not always easy to meet with real-world data

with various orthogonal features. For instance, different types of images require different sparse representations: smooth images are typically sparse in the Fourier domain, while images with sharp edges might be better represented in wavelet or curvelet domains (Lustig et al., 2007). This variability makes it difficult to find the perfect sparse basis, limiting the effectiveness of CS-based methods, especially when data from different modalities are integrated to generalize the performance of the method.

To overcome these limitations, researchers have increasingly turned to deep learning, which has revolutionized many fields, including medical imaging. Deep learning, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs), has shown impressive results in tasks like image classification (Wang et al., 2020), segmentation (Ronneberger et al., 2015), and reconstruction (Zhang and Dong, 2020). In the context of medical imaging, CNNs have been used to enhance the quality of MRI and CT scans (Chen et al., 2017) (Jin et al., 2017)(Wang et al., 2016), offering a more adaptive and data-driven approach to image reconstruction. These models typically require structured CS data as input to produce the best results (Candes, 2008). When dealing with high-resolution MRI images, the network complexity can become overwhelming, which is why it's often necessary to break the data into smaller slices or transform it into a sparse domain before feeding it into the network (He et al., 2016a). In addition to these limitations, such approaches necessitate training the network and adjusting parameters for each specific sampling ratio, as they typically rely on a fixed measurement matrix.

To cope with these issues, this paper takes advantage of an integrated approach that combines a non-iterative CS technique (designed without enforcing sparsity to speed up recovery) with a deep learning-based method to ensure the results meet diagnostic-quality standards. In CS component, this method uses a specified subset of measurements to reconstruct the image, which then serves as the input to the deep learning framework without the need for image slicing, thus accelerating the overall process. Essentially, fewer measurements lead to faster MRI reconstruction. To tackle the under-sampling artifacts that result from using a limited number of measurements, the proposed framework employ a Deep Learning-based Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). As direct access to k-space data is often unavailable from the hospitals due to privacy concerns, we simulate under-sampled measurements from dense images, which are then used as inputs to the deep learning network for validation, which is a true depiction of using real work data, which could be present in any unknown domain.

Additionally, by utilizing a random measurement matrix, the proposed approach enables training the network just once for all possible sampling ratios rather than requiring re-training for each different under-sampling ratio.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 discusses the typical CS technique in the reconstruction domain, the proposed framework, and a variety of deep learning networks to be compared to identify the better network. Section 3 details the experimental materials, while Section 4 presents the results and discussions. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a summary of key findings.

2 METHODS

This paper defines a supervised learning method to help with the problems caused by sparsity-based approaches. This method makes it possible to reconstruct MRI images from data that is not well-sampled without using sparsity constraints.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, a compressed sensing-based approach is first applied to the input data in $\mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$. The image data is then transformed into a \mathbb{R}^M measurement vector by multiplying with a random measurement matrix, where $M \ll N$. The measurement vector is subsequently processed by a fully connected layer to produce a preliminary image proxy.

Figure 1: Measurement images are generated using this procedure for various undersampling ratios.

The resulting image may initially display artifacts and blurring. A deep learning based approach is then utilized to correct the undersampling artifacts, generating a high-resolution reconstruction of the image.

2.1 Compressed Sensing for Image Reconstruction

In CS theory, data consisting of N samples can be mapped into a sparse representation by applying an appropriate sparse transform Ψ , defined as:

$$\theta = \Psi x$$

In CS, the sparse representation of the original image x is denoted by θ , where x comprises N pixels. Sparsity is defined by the condition $\|\theta\|_{\ell_0} \ll N$, with

the ℓ_0 -norm representing the number of non-zero elements in θ . The primary objective of CS is to accurately reconstruct the image x from a reduced set of measurements acquired by the imaging system. Given that the measurement vector y is obtained via a sensing matrix L , the relation between the measurements and the original image can be expressed as:

$$y = Lx$$

In this context, reconstructing the k -space image can be formulated as the following convex optimization problem (Wang et al., 2017),

$$\min \|\theta\|_{\ell_0} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad y = L\Psi^{-1}\theta$$

In this framework, Ψ represents the sparse transform, while L corresponds to the measurement matrix. For CS to be effective, the matrix product $L\Psi$ must exhibit the necessary properties of a valid CS matrix. Minimizing the ℓ_0 -norm, which measures the number of non-zero entries in the sparse representation, typically leads to a combinatorial optimization problem, rendering it computationally impractical for high-resolution image reconstruction. To address this, it has been established that minimizing the ℓ_1 yields equivalent results in most cases, provided the solution is sufficiently sparse. The resulting optimization problem is justified as follows:

$$\min \|\theta\|_{\ell_1} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad y = L\Psi^{-1}\theta$$

In practical scenarios, MRI data often do not exhibit perfect sparsity on a predetermined transform basis, which poses a significant challenge for CS methods to achieve accurate image reconstruction (Provost and Lesage, 2008). A key limitation of CS is its dependency on a reduced number of measurements, even when an optimal sparse basis Ψ is identified. Additionally, as previously discussed, the matrix product $L\Psi$ must satisfy the essential requirements of a CS matrix. Specifically, this matrix must exhibit sufficient linear independence across small subsets of its columns or satisfy the restricted isometry property (RIP) to enable efficient and accurate recovery of the data. As outlined by (Candes, 2008), the RIP condition is defined as:

$$(1 - \delta_s)\|\theta\|_2^2 \leq \|A\theta\|_2^2 \leq (1 + \delta_s)\|\theta\|_2^2$$

where $0 < \delta_s < 1$ is the restricted isometry constant, and $A = L\Psi$ is the sensing matrix. For sparse vectors θ , RIP ensures that any two different sparse vectors can be distinguished from their measurement vectors. Specifically, if two measurement vectors $y_1 = Ax_1$ and $y_2 = Ax_2$ cannot be distinguished, accurate reconstruction of the sparse vectors becomes impossible. Therefore, ensuring that the sensing matrix A satisfies the RIP is critical for successful reconstruction. However, in practice, MRI data typically

do not conform to the perfect sparsity on a fixed basis (Bastounis and Hansen, 2017), leading to failure to meet the RIP condition and consequently limiting the effectiveness of reconstruction.

2.2 Deep Learning Approach

CNN's network architecture is highly important in solving different reconstruction problems. However, choosing an optimal CNN architecture for a given dataset and task is not straightforward. We compared different CNN architectures for MRI reconstructions and quantitatively analyzed their performances individually. The core objective in this framework is to develop a mapping function $\xi : \mathbb{R}^{M \times M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$. The design of such a mapping function assumes the availability of a paired dataset, where each pair consists of a corrupted image V_n and its corresponding artifact-free ground truth Y_n , forming a training set $T = \{(V_n, Y_n)\}_{n=1}^N$. Leveraging deep learning principles, the nonlinear mapping function ξ is learned through an optimization process to minimize the discrepancy between the network output and the ground truth. Specifically, the performance of the mapping function ξ is quantified by the total training error, expressed as (Mousavi and Baraniuk, 2017):

$$E(T; \xi) = \sum_{n=1}^N e(\xi(X_n), Y_n)$$

Here, $e : \mathbb{R}^{N \times N} \times \mathbb{R}^{N \times N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ represents the loss function, which computes the error between the predicted image $\xi(X_n)$ and the true image Y_n during the training process. The ultimate aim is to optimize ξ such that it accurately maps the input measurements to artifact-free, high-quality reconstructions. The various Deep Learning (DL) networks utilized in this study are described as follows:

2.2.1 SegNet

The SegNet architecture (Badrinarayanan et al., 2017) is designed for pixel-wise semantic segmentation based on deep Fully Convolutional Neural Networks. The convolution layers with filter banks followed by batch normalization are applied to produce the set of feature maps in the encoder network. Afterward, element-wise rectified linear (ReLU) non-linearity is formulated as $g(x) = \max(0.0, x)$. To achieve translation invariance in feature maps, max pooling with a (2, 2) window and stride of 2 across many layers is implemented. On the other hand, the decoder network is set to upsample its input feature maps from corresponding encoder feature maps. Besides, to perform non-linear reconstruction of the input image size, the

upsampling is performed based on the indices used in the max-pooling operation of the encoder network. SegNet is proved efficient in terms of both memory and computation time.

2.2.2 UNet

The UNet (Ronneberger et al., 2015) was originally proposed for medical image segmentation and can be trained end-to-end using a small number of samples. It has also shown promising results in photoacoustic microscopy (PAM) and photoacoustic tomography (PAT) image reconstruction and denoising (Guan et al., 2019). The UNet architecture can be viewed as a two-stage network. The first stage consists of a series of encoding layers that increase the number of features while reducing the spatial dimensions of the input image. In the decoding part of the UNet, the latent space features from the encoding part are concatenated with up-sampled layers at each decoder stage to construct the output image. Additionally, the skip concatenation connections within the architecture allow the decoder to learn features that may be lost during the max-pooling operations in the encoder.

Figure 2: The contraction and expansion part of UNet architecture consists of Convolutional operations, max-pooling layers, ReLU activation function, Concatenation, and Upsampling layers.

2.2.3 Residual UNet

After implementing and analyzing the UNet, the recovered images exhibited a degree of over-smoothness. To fix this, we improved the architecture by adding residual blocks. These blocks stop degradation by using skip connections within each block, making it easier for low- and high-level features to move across the network (He et al., 2016b).

The encoder captures feature maps from fine to coarse scales, while the decoder up-samples these maps with residual shortcuts in a coarse-to-fine manner. In the Residual UNet, every two convolutional

Figure 3: Architectural Overview of the Residual UNet (Res-UNet).

layers in the original UNet are replaced with residual blocks, with 1x1 convolutions aligning the input-output feature channels, while all other parameters remain unchanged.

Figure 4: The block module consists of two 3x3 convolutional layers, batch normalization, and ReLU activation, with identity mapping for efficient feature propagation

2.2.4 Fully Dense UNet

Modifying the UNet architecture with dense blocks enables each layer to learn features at different spatial scales, effectively reducing artifacts. The contracting path of the Dense UNet repeatedly reduces spatial dimensions using max-pooling (Guan et al., 2019). In the expanding path, feature maps are upsampled via deconvolution, concatenated with corresponding feature maps from the encoding block, and then refined with 1x1 convolutions before applying the dense block. This dense connectivity enhances image reconstruction quality while reducing network parameters, resulting in lower computational costs and faster reconstruction.

The output of the dense block is concatenated with all previous convolutional layers and learns features

Figure 5: Illustration of the Modified Dense Block in the UNet Architecture.

in a ‘Collective knowledge’ manner through a sequence of 1x1 convolutional and 3x3 convolutional followed by batch normalization and activation function (ReLU). Without the vanishing gradient problem, dense block allows deeper networks and improves computational efficiency by applying 1x1 convolutional to reduced feature-maps before 3x3 convolution.

Figure 6: In dense block, the feature of the previous layer is concatenated together as the input of the following layer.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 Dataset and Training

To evaluate the performance of different Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs), we utilized the MRNet dataset (Ramzi et al., 2020) from Stanford, which contains knee MRI scans acquired in three standard imaging planes: coronal, sagittal, and axial. Specifically, the T1-weighted sequences in the coronal plane were used for this study. The MRNet dataset comprises a series of images with an average intensity mean and standard deviation of 31.48 and 7.97, respectively (Bien et al., 2018). However, some images within the series reveal poor anatomical visibility, which could impact training. These low-quality images were removed as part of the data preprocessing, resulting in a refined dataset. From the T1-weighted coronal sequences, a total of 11,280 images

with a resolution of 256x256 pixels were extracted from 1,370 knee MRI series. The models were trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 over 100 epochs for each undersampling ratio. All neural networks were implemented using Python 3.7.8 with TensorFlow and PyTorch frameworks. The training was conducted on a system equipped with 32 GB RAM and an NVIDIA V100 GPU with 12 GB of memory.

3.2 Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the performance of different deep learning models, different image quality assessment metrics are formulated, such as

3.2.1 Mean Square Error (MSE)

The MSE is the simplest and most complete reference matrix approach used to assess the quality of the image. To estimate the average squared difference between the predicted images and actual images, MSE between two image matrices M and N is defined as:

$$\text{MSE}(M, N) = \frac{1}{AB} \sum_{i=1}^{A-1} \sum_{j=1}^{B-1} (M_{ij} - N_{ij})^2$$

3.2.2 Peak Signal to noise ratio (PSNR)

It is mostly used to control the digital signal transmission quality. PSNR is a variation of MSE that strengthens the pixel-by-pixel comparison (Hore and Ziou, 2010). To calculate the PSNR value between the actual image A and reference image B with the same size $M \times N$ is defined as,

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\max_{image}^2}{\text{MSE}} \right)$$

The greater the PSNR value represents, the higher the predicted image quality.

3.2.3 Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM)

A well-known quality matrix is used to measure the structural similarity between two images that gives the normalized mean value. In the image domain, the more important visual object information spatially closed pixels refer to structure information (Hore and Ziou, 2010). To calculate the image distortion, the SSIM model used three factors such as loss of correlation, luminance distortion, and contrast distortion. The simplified equation of SSIM is defined as,

$$\text{SSIM}(A, B) = \frac{(2\mu_A\mu_B + C_1)(2\sigma_{AB} + C_2)}{(\mu_A^2 + \mu_B^2 + C_1)(\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2 + C_2)} \quad (10)$$

Figure 7: Comparison of reconstruction results for various models at an undersampling ratio of 0.5. The top row presents the ground truth image alongside the predictions from different models, while the bottom row shows the difference maps between the ground truth and predicted images, effectively highlighting the performance of each model.”

Here, μ_A and μ_B are the local means, σ_A^2 and σ_B^2 are the variances, σ_{AB} is the covariance, and C_1 and C_2 are constants used to stabilize the division. The SSIM index is within the range $[0, 1]$, where 0 indicates no correlation between the images and 1 indicates that the actual image and predicted image are identical, $A = B$.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A comprehensive comparison of DL-based advanced image reconstruction techniques is performed by taking the CS method as a baseline, as illustrated in Figure 7.

As envisaged, the DL methods are capable of reconstructing artifactual data with high efficiency, taking into account features such as edges, luminance, contrast, etc. The highlighted red box in Figure 7 visualizes that the proposed network not only removes the under-sampled artifacts but also recovers the minute details of the reconstructed images. In essence, compared with other deep models, Fully Dense UNet (FD-UNet) outperformed in recovering fine details and reducing the over-smoothness observed in images predicted by other methods even in the least favorable scenarios (i.e., lowest sampling ratio). On the other hand, CS-based TV minimization is unable to recover the image with an acceptable diagnostic quality.

Taking into account the quantitative analysis, based on the pre-defined evaluation metrics such as average SSIM and PSNR, it can be seen in Figure 8 and 9 that CS-based TV minimization (sparsity-based method) demonstrates the worst performance with just SSIM = 0.314 and PSNR= 14.90dB even for

Figure 8: The average SSIM for the different undersampling ratios between deep learning models and TV-Minimization.

better working conditions such as undersampling ratio of 0.5. Meanwhile, DL-based methods exhibit superior performance, for instance, with an approximate average SSIM= 0.820 – 0.830 and PSNR = 24 – 26dB for simple UNet, Residual UNet, SegNet under the under-sampling ratio of just 0.2 (using 20% of the total measurements). Additionally to highlight, as discussed in qualitative discussion, UNet and SegNet experience over-smoothing issue; however, the problem is not fully evident in quantitative analysis. Besides FD-UNet outperformed all other methods having SSIM = 0.84 and PSNR= 27 dB and significantly reduces the over smoothing problem to a great extent under the same undersampling conditions i.e. 0.2.

Providing further interpretation and wrapping up the discussion, Figure 10 depicts the comparison of each stage under a challenging scenario (using only 10% measurements) where the top row, (a) represents the measurement image obtained with an undersam-

Figure 9: The average PSNR (db) for different sampling ratio on test samples

Figure 10: Predicted Results using 10% of actual image data

pling ratio of 0.1, and (b) shows the reconstructed image predicted by the FD-UNet model. Subsequently, in the bottom row, (c) represents the actual ground truth image, and (d) is the corresponding difference between the FD-UNet predicted image and the ground truth. In the predicted image, some over-smoothing is identified, causing some details to be sacked.

Overall, in comparison to other neural networks, UNet performs better and has the ability to recover images but it is difficult to train and is vulnerable to over-fitting due to integrated different layers. The incorporation of the different residual blocks, dense block, and inception block may help to improve the performance. Here, in our scenario, the dense block with skip connection improves the performance in retrieving undersampled images because more potential information and features are extracted

in the contracting path, and concatenating the feature map learns more information from a different layer of the network. Moreover, dense connection avoids the learning of redundant features, enhances information flow, and further reduces network parameters on the premise of close performance. The reduction of network parameters reduces the calculation cost, and the image reconstruction can be faster. Overall, our experiments showed that the recovery of real-world medical data is possible using DL-based algorithms with better diagnostic image quality and improved performance in comparison with traditional CS-based methods.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

As recently, deep CNNs based networks are being popular to remove artifacts and denoise the reconstructed medical images. In this article, we compare the performance of different deep-learning models with the help of synthetic data for real-world medical data image recovery without considering any constraints. The experimental results show that a fully dense UNet has a better image-recovering effect under the premise of fewer measurements. However, these end-to-end recovering methods reconstruct the image in just less than one second with the help of a well-trained network. This method allows real-time recovery of artifact images without delays. Future efforts should focus on developing more advanced networks to capture finer details with lower computational costs. Additionally, refining existing architectures or introducing new ones could lead to further performance improvements.

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